

THE EFFECT OF SPIRITUALITY AT WORK ON KNOWLEDGE SHARING AND JOB PERFORMANCE ALONG WITH THE MODERATING EFFECT OF WORK ENGAGEMENT AND WORKPLACE VIOLENCE

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Abstract

Spirituality is a life-giving and motivating force, an energy that inspires a person towards a certain goal or a goal beyond individuality. The purpose of this research is to investigate the effect of spirituality at work on knowledge and job performance along with the moderating effect of job engagement and Workplace violence. The research is a descriptive survey study in which 132 professors and employees of Payame Noor University of Tehran participated. The data were analyzed using path analysis test and SPSS 23 and Lisrel 8.75 software. The results of the research indicate that organizations that have spirituality can increase job engagement and reduce withdrawal behavior by creating motivation, providing information and delegating authority, and provide opportunities for empowering and improving the performance of employees.

Keywords: Spirituality at Work, Work Engagement, Workplace Violence, Knowledge Sharing, Job Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Paying attention to employees and, above all, their job performance as the biggest and most important capital of the organization is a phenomenon that has grown a lot in the last few decades (Abdulwahab, 2016). The biggest challenge in employee job performance is motivating members to share their knowledge with others. Employees who are reluctant to share knowledge are unsuccessful in sharing knowledge, which in turn leads to work inefficiency, high errors, and poor work quality (Wang & Noe, 2010). Meanwhile, wherever employees work, they are looking for something beyond material rewards in work, they are looking for a meaningful, hopeful and demanding work to balance their lives. In other words, organizations are faced with employees who seek to find work with meaning, purpose and, in general, spirituality at work (Shen et al., 2009).

Spirituality at work is a special situation that has spiritual, emotional and cognitive dimensions. Spirituality includes attractive work, which features; It is a favorable feeling, well-being and belief in doing meaningful work that pursues a high goal, as well as the alignment of one's values, work beliefs, and a sense of independence with this characteristic of having a spiritual connection with something higher than oneself, and experiencing a sense of solidarity, which is the same. It involves a sense of connection with others and a common goal (Kinjerski & Skrypnek, 2004).

Spirituality causes people in the workplace to display more teamwork and behave more kindly and fairly (Mitroff & Denton, 1999) and to be more sensitive to the needs of other employees (Cash et al., 2000), show more trust, trustworthiness and honesty in the organization (Krishnakumar & Neck, 2002), and have a higher organizational commitment (Kinjerski & Skrypnek, 2006).

It seems that spirituality in the workplace can have a significant impact on the job engagement of employees and the reduction of withdrawal behavior. In many organizations, the engage of the employees in their work is not favorable and this case has resulted in exorbitant costs for the organization. Research shows that only 18% of the global workforce has job passion and more than half of the workforce would not recommend their current employer to their colleagues (Deloitte, 2016). Employees who have job passion show higher performance, they are interested in their job, they try to fulfill their job duties, and they have great stability when faced with problems and difficulty of work (Poyafar et al., 2016). Employees engaged in work are completely attracted to their jobs and perform their job tasks well (Bakker & Leiter, 2010).

Violence is also a part of occupational hazards related to the work environment. Workplace violence can have devastating effects on employees. The experience of physical and non-physical violence among employees is associated with a decrease in self-confidence, job satisfaction and quality of life, leaving the job, increasing anxiety and job pressure (Choi & Lee, 2017).

Workplace violence may be experienced in different forms, including physical, emotional, or verbal (Mckenna & Boyle, 2016), which co-workers, supervisors, subordinates, and other professional groups play a role in creating (Camerino et al., 2008). In the national document for promoting the mental health of the country, violence is recognized both as one of the factors and as one of the consequences of mental health disorders, and the implementation of the violence prevention program is recommended as one of the basic interventions of the first level of prevention (Hajebi et al, 2013). Of course, the studies conducted on the prevalence of violence in the workplace in Iran have been limited to healthcare workers such as nurses (Azami et al., 2018; Sahebi et al., 2019).

Regarding international researches, individual factors including characteristics and mental disorders in employees as well as organizational factors such as excessive workload, supervisory systems, incentive systems and management styles have been implicated in the occurrence of violence in the workplace (Ariza-Montes et al., 2014).

Considering that the university environment is an important human environment, on the one hand, many people nowadays feel dissatisfied, restless and insecure in their work, so addressing the category of spirituality in the workplace and its impact on workplace violence, Work engagement, sharing Knowledge and job performance of university employees is essential. The study of spirituality in the working environment of university employees can help the university to facilitate and accelerate the achievement of its goals and mission.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF RESEARCH

2.1. Job performance and knowledge sharing

In general, job performance is defined by the general values expected by the organization from different organizational departments, which are presented separately by the active people in that department, and each person performs it during a certain period of time (Platis et al., 2015). This is despite the fact that knowledge is the vital force of the organization and the factor of its survival in the current competitive era (Asrar-ul-Haq & Anwar, 2016). Although some believe that knowledge is power, it seems that knowledge in itself does not have power; Rather, what gives people power is the part of their knowledge that they share with others (O Dell & Grayson, 1998). If individual knowledge is not accessible and used by other people, it will not affect the organization (Law & Ngai, 2008). Knowledge sharing is defined as mutual social culture, which includes the exchange of employees' knowledge, experiences and skills through all departments of the organization (Lin, 2007). Knowledge sharing activities are divided into two categories of open and hidden knowledge sharing (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995). In open knowledge sharing, people distribute information obtained from different sources to others, and in hidden knowledge sharing, employees share hidden knowledge through conversations and thinking about their experiences (Coakes, 2006). Explicit knowledge sharing activities are more common in the workplace because explicit knowledge can be easily absorbed, codified and transferred. Organizational procedures, official language, manuals, and information technology systems are tools for knowledge sharing and can increase employees' willingness to do so (Huang et al., 2010). But hidden knowledge is more personal due to its nature and its explanation is difficult for the possessor of the knowledge. This feature causes complexity and intangible knowledge and makes it difficult to transfer it completely and at once (Van-Wijk et al., 2008). As a result of mutual interactions between people, they are the primary means of sharing hidden knowledge (Ghorbanizadeh & Khaleghinia, 2008). Human experiences are fundamental in sharing tacit knowledge, and the factors affecting it include people's willingness and capacity to share what they know and to use what they learn (Holste & Fields, 2010). In general, in today's organizations, work is so dependent on teamwork and collective knowledge that instead of simply encouraging employees to share knowledge, it is better to identify the factors affecting knowledge sharing (O Dell & Grayson, 1998).

2.2. Spirituality in the workplace

Spirituality in the work environment, which is one of the main trends in the 21st century, can play an important role in increasing the willingness of employees to share their knowledge and job performance. Spirituality at work refers to the employee's effort to find meaning and purpose at work (Afsar & Badir, 2017). Spirituality in the workplace includes trying to find the ultimate goal of a person in life, establishing a strong relationship with colleagues and other people related to work, and compatibility between personal beliefs and organizational values (Milliman et al., 2003). In this way, spirituality has three dimensions that correspond to three individual, group and organizational levels: meaningful work at the individual level, sense of belonging at the group level and alignment with the values of the organization at the organizational level.

A fundamental aspect of spirituality at work includes a deep sense of meaning and purpose at work. This dimension of spirituality in the work environment determines how employees interact in their daily work at an individual level. The expression of spirituality in work includes the assumption that every person has internal motivation, desire and interests to undertake activities that give more meaning to his life and others. Another essential dimension of spirituality in the work environment includes a kind of feeling of connection and feeling of deep connection with others (Ashmos & Duchon, 2000). This dimension of spirituality in the work environment occurs at the group level of human behavior and implies the interactions between employees and colleagues. Correlation in the work environment is based on the belief that people know each other in connection with each other and that there is a relationship between the inner self of each person and the inner self of others (Milliman et al., 2003), this level of spirituality in the work environment includes mental communication, It is emotional and spiritual between employees in work groups.

The third dimension of workplace spirituality is the experience of a strong sense of alignment between the individual values of employees with the organization's mission, vision, and values. This dimension of spirituality in the work environment includes the interaction of employees with the larger organizational purpose (Mitroff & Denton, 1999). Alignment with the organization's values means that people believe that managers and employees in the organization have relevant values and a strong conscience, and that the organization cares about the welfare of employees and their solidarity (Ashmos & Duchon, 2000).

Researchers state that encouraging spirituality in the work environment can lead to advantages and benefits such as increased creativity (Freshman, 1999), increased honesty and trust (Wanger-Marsh & Conley, 1999), increased sense of personal development (Burack, 1999), increased organizational commitment. improving the job attitudes of employees such as increasing job satisfaction, job participation and also reducing the desire to leave the work environment (Milliman et al., 2003), and all of these directly and indirectly lead to improvement Performance, profitability and organizational effectiveness.

2.3. Work engagement

The concept of Work engagement was introduced in the 19th century. Kahn (1990) has defined Work engagement as the application and expression of a person's preference in work behaviors, personal presence (physical, cognitive and emotional) and active and full role performance. Hewitt (2004) believes Work engagement of employees is the amount of engage and interest that employees have in their organization.

Hallberg & Schaufeli (2006) consider Work engagement as a positive psychological concept and is known as an indicator of well-being and psychological health in the workplace. Employees engaged in work are characterized by low neuroticism, extroversion and high flexibility (Langelaan et al., 2006). Work engagement of employees has three cognitive, emotional and behavioral aspects. The cognitive aspect of Work engagement is related to employees' beliefs about the organization, leaders, and working conditions. The emotional aspect of Work engagement is related to how employees feel and their attitude towards the

organization, leaders and working conditions. Finally, the behavioral aspect of employees' Work engagement is a factor that creates added value for the organization and includes the conscious and voluntary efforts of employees to increase the level of their Work engagement, which leads to performing tasks with more time and interest (Phillips & Roper, 2009).

Employees engaged in work have high levels of energy, are passionate about their work, and are often completely immersed in their work. In modern organizations, employees are expected to be active and take initiative, take responsibility for their own professional development, and commit to high quality performance standards.

2.4. Violence in the workplace

Workplace violence is a global problem whose dimensions are expanding and its prevalence in different work environments shows a significant difference (Nielsen & Einarsen, 2018). According to the definition of the International Labor Organization, violence in the workplace refers to a set of unacceptable behaviors and actions or threats that are carried out as a single or repeated incident intentionally and lead to physical, psychological, sexual or economic damage to employees. It can be done (Beqiraj, 2019). Workplace violence is defined as cases in which employees are harassed, threatened or attacked in their work environment (World Health Organization, 2002). Based on the findings of international studies, workplace violence with a higher risk of negative mental health outcomes such as psychological suffering, anxiety, sleep disorders, chronic fatigue, depression, adjustment disorder and even work-related suicide (Chan et al., 2019) and complications A body such as muscle and skeletal pain, cardiovascular diseases and type 2 diabetes are related (Xu et al., 2018). In addition to affecting the health and well-being of employees, violence in the workplace is associated with an increased risk for a range of social and economic problems in the workplace. These problems include frequent absences from work, long absences due to illness, reduced productivity and increased unemployment (Sansone & Sansone, 2015).

2.5. Conceptual model and research assumptions

The study of the previous research led the researcher to investigate two paths in this research. First, a more complete investigation of the impact of spirituality at work (meaningful work, group sense, and alignment with organizational values) on job performance, and another investigation of the impact of spirituality in the workplace on job performance and knowledge sharing along with the moderating effect of Work engagement and violence in the workplace. According to the presented conceptual framework, the hypotheses and conceptual model of the research (Fig 1) are presented as follows.

Fig 1: The conceptual model of research

2.6. Research assumptions

- Hypothesis 1. Spirituality at work has a significant effect on violence in the workplace.
- Hypothesis 2. Spirituality at work has a significant effect on Work engagement.
- Hypothesis 3. Spirituality at work has a significant effect on knowledge sharing
- Hypothesis 4. Spirituality at work has a significant effect on job performance.
- Hypothesis 5. Violence at work has a significant effect on knowledge sharing.
- Hypothesis 6. Violence at work has a significant effect on job performance.
- Hypothesis 7. Work engagement has a significant effect on knowledge sharing.
- Hypothesis 8. Work engagement has a significant effect on job performance.
- Hypothesis 9. Violence in the workplace has a significant effect on Work engagement.
- Hypothesis 10. Knowledge sharing has a significant effect on job performance.

3. METHODS

3.1. Participants and procedure

The present research in terms of purpose; practical and in terms of method; It is descriptive-survey. The statistical population of this research includes 210 employees and professors of Payame Noor University in Tehran. Sampling of the population was done according to the relevant ratio and the required number of samples was obtained using Morgan's method equal to 132 people. Sampling from the community was done randomly. Since it was possible that some of the questionnaires were not returned or were incompletely completed, the calculated sample was distributed with an increase of about 10%. According to the return rate of 135 questionnaires, which shows a significant return rate and an acceptable number, the aforementioned data were used for further analysis.

3.2. Measuring instruments

The data collection tool in this research is the questionnaire.

3.2.1. Spirituality at work.

We adopted the 11-item scale of spirituality at work, which Milliman et al. (2003) used to measure spirituality in the workplace using this scale with 21 items. We reduced the number of items in this study. Some items that the employees expressed their opinion on through a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 5= strongly agree) include: I enjoy my work, cooperation with others is valuable, and the organization cares about all its employees. We found the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this scale to be $\alpha=0.95$.

3.2.2. Knowledge sharing.

We adopted the 5-item knowledge sharing scale that Bock et al. (2005) used to measure implicit and explicit knowledge sharing. Some of the items that the employees expressed their opinion about through a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 5= strongly agree): I share my experience and knowledge with my colleagues, if needed, I share reports and authorized work documents with my colleagues. We found the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this scale to be $\alpha= 0.97$.

3.2.3. Work engagement.

We adopted the 8-item work engagement scale that Rich et al. (2010) used to measure work engagement using this scale with 18 items. We reduced the number of subjects in this study. Some of the items that the employees expressed their opinion about through a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree ; 5= strongly agree) include: I put a lot of energy into my work, I feel positive about my job, and at work, my mind is focused on my work. We found the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this scale to be $\alpha= 0.98$.

3.2.4. Workplace violence.

We adopted a 7-item scale of violence in the workplace, in which the items of Hader 's scale (2008) were used, in which employees expressed their opinions about physical violence, verbal violence, psychological violence, sexual harassment, racial and religious harassment through a five-point Likert scale (1=low ; 5= high). We found the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this scale to be $\alpha= 0.96$.

3.2.5. Job performance.

We adopted the 7-item job performance scale that Williams & Anderson (1991) used to measure job performance with 21 items. We reduced the number of subjects in this study. Some of the items that the employees expressed their opinion on through a five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree ; 5= strongly agree) include: I perform the tasks set in my job, I fulfill the requirements that have been set and I have to do in my job, I behave friendly and help clients. We found the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient for this scale to be $\alpha=0.94$.

3.3. Analytical strategy

In the next stage, a survey was conducted and after that the research factors were analyzed using the path analysis method. This study was conducted by observing ethical considerations and also explaining the objectives of the research to the research units, the confidentiality of information by not writing the name and surname in the questionnaire, the willingness to participate and the right to choose for the research units.

4. RESULTS

In the present study, most of the studied people; (48.5%) in the age group of 30-39 years, women (58%) and married (74%). 65.4% of the researched samples also had a bachelor's degree. To ensure the normality of the studied variables, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used. The results show that all the variables are not statistically significantly different from the normal distribution. Therefore, the assumption of normality of research variables was confirmed. After confirming the normality, linearity and homogeneity of the variances for the two-way relationship between the variables, all the relationships between the variables were examined. It should be mentioned that in order to confirm the structural model or the path diagram, first the t values and standard coefficients should be significant and then, its indices should have a suitable fit (Table 1). According to the research findings in Table 1, knowledge sharing ($\beta = 0.04$, $p \leq 0.05$), and spirituality at work ($\beta = 0.36$, $p \leq 0.05$) have a positive and direct effect on job performance.

Table 1: Relationship values between variables in the initial research model

Relationships	Estimate value	T value	P value	Hypothesis testing
Spirituality at work × Workplace violence	-0.81	-12.68	$p \leq 0.05$	H1 Accepted
Spirituality at work × Work engagement	0.88	13.29	$p \leq 0.05$	H2 Accepted
Spirituality at work × Knowledge sharing	2.33	2.38	$p \leq 0.05$	H3 Accepted
Spirituality at work × Job performance	0.36	3.89	$p \leq 0.05$	H4 Accepted
Workplace violence × Knowledge sharing	0.98	1.58	$p \geq 0.05$	H5 Not Accepted
Workplace violence × Job performance	-0.06	-1.09	$p \geq 0.05$	H6 Not Accepted
Work engagement × Knowledge sharing	3.72	4.45	$p \leq 0.05$	H7 Accepted
Work engagement × Job performance	0.16	1.94	$p \geq 0.05$	H8 Not Accepted
Workplace violence × Work engagement	-0.24	-3.99	$p \leq 0.05$	H9 Accepted
Knowledge sharing × Job performance	0.04	5.16	$p \leq 0.05$	H10 Accepted

But workplace violence and Work engagement did not have a direct and significant effect on job performance ($p \geq 0.05$). Work engagement ($\beta = 3.72$, $p \leq 0.05$), and spirituality at work ($\beta = 2.33$, $p \leq 0.05$) have a positive and direct effect on knowledge sharing, but workplace violence did not have a direct and significant effect on knowledge sharing ($p \geq 0.05$). Workplace violence ($\beta = -0.24$, $p \leq 0.05$), and spirituality at work ($\beta = 0.88$, $p \leq 0.05$) have direct effect on Work engagement, as well as spirituality at work ($\beta = -0.81$, $p \leq 0.05$) had a significant and inverse effect on violence in the workplace. Based on this, the estimated values of direct relationships between model variables that do not have a statistically significant value ($P > 0.05$) should be removed from the initial model to estimate the values of the final model (fig 2). According to the research findings in Table 2, knowledge sharing ($\beta = 0.05$, $p \leq 0.00$), and spirituality at work

($\beta = 0.56, p \leq 0.00$) have a positive and direct effect on job performance. Work engagement ($\beta = 3.29, p \leq 0.00$), and spirituality at work ($\beta = 2.00, p \leq 0.05$) have a positive and direct effect on knowledge sharing. Workplace violence ($\beta = -0.24, p \leq 0.01$), and spirituality at work ($\beta = 0.88, p \leq 0.00$) have a positive and direct effect on Work engagement, as well as spirituality at work ($\beta = -0.81, p \leq 0.00$) had a significant and inverse effect on violence in the workplace.

Table 2: Relationship values between variables in the final research model

Relationships	Estimate value	P value
knowledge sharing × Job performance	0.05	$p \leq 0.05$
Spirituality at work × Job performance	0.56	$p \leq 0.05$
Work engagement × Knowledge sharing	3.29	$p \leq 0.05$
Spirituality at work × Knowledge sharing	2.00	$p \leq 0.05$
Workplace violence × Work engagement	-0.24	$p \leq 0.05$
Spirituality at work × Work engagement	0.88	$p \leq 0.05$
Spirituality at work × Workplace violence	-0.81	$p \leq 0.05$

Fig 2: T-values in the final research model

Another research finding is that according to chart 3 and according to the value of R square, 76% of changes in job performance are related to the effect of variables outside the model and 24% of the causes of job performance are due to the effect of variables in the model. Also, 57% of the changes in knowledge sharing are related to the effect of variables outside the model and

43% of the causes of knowledge sharing are due to the effect of the variables in the model. Finally, the indicators related to the fit of the pattern of their final path show a very good fit of the pattern. The pattern fit test determines whether the proposed pattern should be accepted or not. The value of fit indices shows that the research model is acceptable and desirable (Table 3).

Table 3: Fit indicators of the final model

Fit measures	Recommended values	Value	Comment
NFI	NFI>0.90	0.99	Fitted
NNFI	NNFI >0.90	0.97	Fitted
GFI	GFI >0.90	0.97	Fitted
IFI	IFI >0.90	0.99	Fitted
X ² /df	X ² /df < 3	2.24	Fitted

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The present study sought to investigate the effect of spirituality at work on knowledge sharing and job performance along with the mediation of workplace violence and Work engagement in professors and employees of Payame Noor University in Tehran. The results showed that spirituality at work has an effect on reducing the amount of violence at work. This finding is in line with the research results of Saleh (2020), Ghalandari (2020), Mat Sohaa et al (2016). It seems that spirituality at work can help a lot to understand issues related to leadership and management.

Creating a positive and supportive environment by enhancing the sense of belonging to the organization and the feeling of being valuable among the employees will reduce the tension and violence at work. Violence in the workplace may cause physical and mental injuries to employees. Therefore, by promoting organizational spirituality, the manager will be the foundation for preventing possible consequences. On the other hand, strengthening spirituality in the work environment will increase employees' engage in work.

The results of the research of Molai et al. (2014), Hakimi (2018), Gharibzadeh & Alizadeh (2017), also confirm this finding, since engage in work causes enthusiasm, commitment, engagement with work, energy and pleasant work can have positive effects on the performance of the individual and the organization.

Spirituality at work also has a positive effect on increasing the willingness to share knowledge. The research results of Ghanbarpour Nosrati et al. (2018) are in line with this finding. Organizations have used various motivational factors to show that they are determined and serious in the field of knowledge sharing in their organization. In knowledge-based organizations, recognition and reward programs have been considered for people who provide their knowledge to others. Some other companies evaluate their employees based on the extent to which they have participated in knowledge sharing activities and consider promotions or extraordinary leaves for them.

This hypothesis shows that spirituality in the workplace can also play an important role in creating a work environment that encourages knowledge sharing behavior. And in general, spirituality in the workplace plays an important role in improving the job performance of employees. This finding agrees with the research results of Saleh (2020), and Albuquerque et al. (2014).

This powerful force in the organization will be achieved when the working life is connected with the spiritual life of the employees. Because the structure of spirituality in the work environment consists of dimensions of sense of meaning and purpose in work, honesty and dedication, altruism and consecration of life.

Informing managers about the existence of such valuable factors and how to use them in advancing organizational goals can have a significant impact on improving the organization's performance. But on the other hand, violence at work had a negative effect on Work engagement directly and knowledge sharing indirectly.

In traditional models, organizations and individuals often have no desire to transfer and share the knowledge they have and instead of looking at knowledge as a scientific capital, they consider it as a source of power, a lever of influence and a guarantee of their job continuity. They did not want to share it with others, while the findings show that culture, cooperation and commitment are the three key components in knowledge sharing, and violence in the workplace can be an obstacle to cooperation and information exchange in the organization, and ultimately to indirect job performance.

Have a negative effect. But Work engagement has an indirect effect on knowledge sharing. Often, people cannot understand how useful a certain knowledge can be for others. A person may have knowledge that he can use in a specific situation, not knowing that it can be useful for other people in other times and places and similar cases or can be a stimulus for creativity and innovation. In this regard, engage in work can be a strong driver for sharing knowledge in the organization and cause many improvements within the organization.

The findings show that Work engagement is one of the factors that indirectly affects the job performance of employees. This finding is in line with the research results of Cheraghi et al (2012). It is the engage of employees in work that will lead them to the workplace, and if employees are aware of the meaning of their work, they will increase their motivation to do better work. And finally, knowledge sharing was also effective in improving the job performance of employees, and it is in line with the findings of Keshvarzi et al (2015).

In sum, the results of the research indicate that in knowledge-based organizations, spirituality as a stable source for the organization can have a positive effect on knowledge sharing and the job performance of employees. Organizations that have spirituality can increase Work engagement and reduce violence in the workplace by creating motivation, providing information and delegating authority, and empowering and improving the performance of employees. Based on the findings of the research, suggestions are made: All the complaints and concerns of the employees should be listened to.

Be informed and accurate about sudden changes and changes in behavior patterns, plan easy ways to access communication channels and support systems, and implement a clear method that cannot be manipulated and employees can use those aggressions against them. Report that it has been implemented.

Pay attention to the human character of the employees and give it importance. The thoughts, ideas, initiatives and suggestions of the employees should be taken into account and welcomed. Also, try to create a friendly atmosphere based on participation and cooperation and eliminate other constructive competitions by reducing stress and strengthening the solidarity and harmony of employees as social assets.

The most important limitation of the present research is the bias in the common methodology. However, much effort was made to ensure confidentiality and the importance of respondents' honesty. Also, standard scales, tests and questionnaires were used to reduce the effects of research methodology through reliable data collection and measurements.

Since this research was conducted in Payame Noor University, it is suggested that it be conducted in other public and private production or service organizations and companies and the results are compared with the present research.

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